

Formulation And Evaluation Of Pentoxifylline Film – Forming Spray For Acute Wound Healing

R Gayathri^{*1}, M. Kesavan², P. Kavin Prabhu³, G. Varshini⁴, Gi Mani Bharathi⁵, T. Kathires⁶

Department of pharmaceutics, KMCH College of pharmacy, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

Background: The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of Pentoxifylline loaded film-forming sprays designed for topical application. Pentoxifylline, a xanthine derivative, is known for its vasodilatory and anti-inflammatory properties, making it a promising candidate for transdermal drug delivery. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) was used as the film-forming polymer at 2% and 4% concentration, while polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) and glycerin served as plasticizers to enhance film flexibility and drug releases. **Materials and Methods:** Four formulations (F1, F2, F3 and F4) were developed, with F1 and F2 containing 2% HPMC and 0.5% PEG 400 and glycerin, whereas F3 and F4 contained 4% HPMC along with the same plasticizer concentration. **Results:** The prepared formulations were evaluated for spray characteristics, film-forming ability, drying time, mechanical properties, and *In vitro* drug release studies revealed that formulations with lower HPMC concentrations exhibited faster drug diffusion, whereas higher polymer concentrations provided more sustained release. **Conclusion:** The study demonstrates the potential of Pentoxifylline loaded film-forming sprays as an effective topical drug delivery system with enhanced patient compliance and controlled drug release. Further *ex vivo* skin permeation studies and *In vivo* efficacy assessment are warranted to confirm their therapeutic applicability.

Keywords: Pentoxifylline, Film-forming spray, HPMC, Plasticizer, *In vitro* drug release, Topical drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Pentoxifylline also known as Pentoxifylline methylxanthines derivative that modulates rheological properties of blood and also had both anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. (1)(2) A product of methylxanthines, Pentoxifylline also has anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant qualities and modulates the rheological characteristics of blood. The initial purpose of Pentoxifylline was to alleviate intermittent claudication, a kind of leg discomfort brought on by effort that is frequently experienced by individuals with peripheral artery disorders.(3)(4) The potential application of PTX has been studied in a variety of conditions, such as osteoradionecrosis, diabetes, renal illnesses, and typically any fibrosis-related ailment.(3)(5)(6) Due to its capacity to control the synthesis of inflammatory cytokines, PTX has more recently been proposed as a potential therapy for COVID-19 induced liver

complication.(7)Pentoxifylline has been shown to speed up the healing of wounds in diabetic ulcer patients and venous ulcer patients, as well as in animal models. However, due to its poor bioavailability due to hepatic first-pass metabolism, it was discovered that oral administration of Pentoxifylline had no meaningful influence on the rates of chronic wound healing. Pentoxifylline might therefore be directly administered orally through the development of an appropriate topical delivery method. (8)As a phosphodiesterase inhibitor, Pentoxifylline raises the levels of cyclic AMP by inhibiting the membrane-bound phosphodiesterase. Additionally, the medication promotes the production of prostacyclin and inhibits the synthesis of thromboxane. Platelet aggregation is decreased as a result of these processes. Furthermore, in individuals with circulatory problems, Pentoxifylline has been shown to reduce platelet adherence to the artery wall. (9)

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It like other methylated xanthine derivatives, is a competitive nonselective phosphodiesterase inhibitor(10) that decreases inflammation and innate immunity, increases intracellular cAMP, activates PKA, inhibits TNF⁽¹¹⁾⁽¹²⁾, and leukotriene production.(13) Pentoxifylline also lowers blood viscosity, enhances red blood cell deformability (often referred to as the hemorheological effect), and lessens the risk of platelet aggregation and blood clot formation.(14) Additionally, Pentoxifylline inhibits the adenosine 2 receptor.(15)PTX is the cause of the decrease in matrix metalloproteinase 1 (MMP-1) and MMP-1 and MMP- 3 gene expression and the rise in genes expressing the tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase (TIM- 1). It has an impact on the extracellular matrix metalloproteinase quantitative expression, which is in charge of tissue remodeling and healing after damage. (16)(17)By decreasing the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and boosting the activity of antioxidant enzymes in tissue, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase, PTX lessens oxidative stress. It also modifies the expression of genes linked to inflammation and oxidative stress, which may further enhance its healing effects. Vitamin C&E has better antioxidant activity than other quinacrine and is more efficient in preventing lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress.(18)(19)

WOUND HEALING AND INFECTION:

A wound results from the breakdown of the epidermal layer, leading to potential infections that may delay healing. Proliferation, remodelling, and inflammation are the three overlapping stages of wound healing begins immediately with hemostasis, where clotting forms a fibrin plug to stop bleeding, followed by vasoconstriction and vasodilation. Platelets release factors that recruit neutrophils for phagocytosis, ROS release, and cytokine signaling. The proliferative

phase (days 3-10) involves granulation tissue formation, fibroblast proliferation, angiogenesis, and epithelialization, driven by growth factors like TGF-beta and VEGF. The remodeling phase (day 21-1 year) strengthens tissue as type III collagen is replaced by type I, ECM is reorganized by MMPs, and myofibroblasts contract the wound. Angiogenesis ceases, and scars reach about 80% of normal skin strength after three months.

FILM FORMING SPRAY AND ITS MECHANISM:

Film-forming spray creates a protective, flexible, and waterproof barrier on wounds, maintaining a moist environment for healing while delivering the active ingredient. This barrier shields against contaminants, reducing infection risk and accelerating recovery.

POLYMERS AND PLASTICIZERS:

Polymers play a crucial role in film-forming sprays by aiding film development, regulating drug release, and ensuring stability. Both natural (e.g., ethyl cellulose, HPMC, chitosan) and synthetic polymers (e.g., Carbopol, Eudragit) offer unique properties such as biodegradability, viscoelasticity, and pH or temperature sensitivity. Plasticizers like PEG and PG maintain film elasticity, prevent cracking, and enhance drug penetration. Solvents, both volatile and non-volatile, influence film drying rates, ensuring optimal drug release without compromising film flexibility. Balancing these components is key to effective film-forming spray formulations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Table 1: List of materials

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	PURPOSE	MANUFACTURERS
1.	Pentoxifylline	API	Bestcare Formulation, Pondicherry
2.	HPMC K100	Polymer	HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd
3.	PEG 400	Plasticizer	Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd
6.	Glycerin	Plasticizer	Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd
7.	Propylene glycol	Plasticizer	BRM Chemicals
8.	Tween-80	Surfactant	Merck Chemicals
9.	Menthol	Counter irritant	Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd
10.	Camphor	Permeation enhancer	Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd
11.	Ethanol	Solvent	Changsu Hongsheng Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd

Table 2: List of equipment's

S.NO	EQUIPMENT	MODEL	MANUFACTURER
1.	Digital weighing machine	AX200	Shimadzu Corporation, Japan
2.	UV- Visible Spectrophotometer	UV-1800	Pharm spec, Shimadzu
3.	FT-IR Spectrophotometer	4100	JASCO
4.	Magnetic stirrer	1MLH	Remi
5.	Glass wares	Borosilicate	Borosil

CHARACTERISTICS OF PRE-FORMULATED SOLUTIONS:

Table 3: Various formulation of Pentoxifylline film forming spray

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4
DRUG (PENTOXIFYLLINE)	5%	5%	5%	5%
HPMC K100	2%	2%	4%	4%
PEG-400	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
GLYCERIN	0.5%	-	0.5%	-
PROPYLENE GLYCOL	-	0.5%	-	0.5%
TWEEN-80	1%	1%	1%	1%
MENTHOL	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%
CAMPBOR	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
ETHANOL	15ml	15ml	20ml	20ml
WATER	10ml	10ml	20ml	20ml

METHOD

To prepare the film-forming solution, begin by dissolving HPMC K100 in ethanol under continuous stirring to ensure proper dispersion and polymer hydration. This step is crucial for achieving a uniform and stable polymer matrix that will support film formation upon application. In a separate container, mix PEG 400, glycerine, and propylene glycol, which act as plasticizers to maintain film elasticity and prevent cracking. To enhance dispersion and drug penetration, add Tween-80, ensuring it is thoroughly blended with the plasticizer solution. Next, dissolve pentoxifylline in the ethanol-polymer mixture while stirring continuously to ensure complete solubility. Incorporate menthol and camphor, which serve as penetration enhancers, improving the drug's absorption through the skin. Once all components are

dissolved, gradually add the plasticizer-surfactant mixture to the polymer-drug solution while maintaining constant stirring to achieve a homogenous solution. To ensure smooth application and prevent inconsistencies, filter the final solution to remove any undissolved particles or impurities. Store the prepared film-forming solution in an airtight spray container, protecting it from light and heat to maintain stability. This formulation allows for the creation of a flexible, uniform film upon application, facilitating controlled drug release, enhanced skin penetration, and improved therapeutic efficacy.

SOLUBILITY:

The solubility study of pentoxifylline was conducted to evaluate its dissolution behaviour in different solvents, including ethanol, chloroform, and water, at

room temperature. In this process, a known quantity of pentoxifylline was added to each solvent, and the mixture was stirred continuously to facilitate dissolution. The samples were then allowed to equilibrate for a specific duration to ensure maximum solubility was reached. After the equilibrium period, the solutions were visually inspected for any undissolved particles, and the solubility of pentoxifylline in each solvent was assessed based on the clarity and homogeneity of the solutions. Additionally, filtration or centrifugation may have been performed to separate undissolved drug particles, followed by spectrophotometric or chromatographic analysis to quantify the amount of pentoxifylline dissolved in each solvent. This study helps determine the most suitable solvent for drug formulation, ensuring optimal solubility and bioavailability in pharmaceutical applications.

MELTING POINT:

The melting point determination of the drug was carried out using a melting point apparatus following an approved protocol to ensure accuracy and reliability. A thin-walled capillary tube was selected, and a small quantity of the medication was carefully introduced into the tube. To prevent the sample from spilling out, one end of the capillary tube was sealed by gently heating it. The capillary tube containing the drug sample was then placed inside the melting point device, ensuring that the sample was correctly positioned for uniform heating. The temperature of the apparatus was gradually increased at a controlled rate to allow precise measurement of the melting point range. Throughout the process, visual inspection was conducted to observe the point at which the drug began to transition from a solid to a liquid state. The onset and completion temperatures of melting were carefully noted, defining the melting point range of the medication. This test helps assess the purity and thermal stability of the drug, as impurities often cause a depression or broadening of the melting range. The recorded melting point was then compared with standard reference values to verify the identity and quality of the drug substance.

FT-IR ANALYSIS:

FT-IR spectroscopy was employed to investigate the molecular interactions between Pentoxifylline (PTX)

and polymers within a film-forming spray formulation, with a particular focus on potential drug-excipient interactions. This analytical technique was utilized to identify any shifts, alterations, or additional peaks that might indicate hydrogen bonding, van der Waals forces, or other intermolecular interactions between the drug and the polymeric excipients.

For this purpose, the FT-IR spectra of pure Pentoxifylline and the physical mixture 1—comprising PTX and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K100)—were recorded using a Jasco FT/IR-4100 spectrophotometer. Spectral data were collected in the range of 600 to 4000 cm^{-1} , enabling the identification of characteristic functional groups and any possible modifications in the vibrational frequencies resulting from molecular interactions. By comparing the FT-IR spectra of the pure drug and the physical mixture, potential compatibility between PTX and HPMC K100 was assessed, providing valuable insight into the stability and performance of the film-forming spray formulation.

The FT-IR study of Pentoxifylline (PTX) revealed characteristic peaks at 1215.9, 1705.73, 1597.73, 2949.59, and 3355.63 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-N stretching (amide bond), C=O stretching (amine group), N-H bending (secondary amine), C-H stretching (aliphatic group), and N-H stretching (secondary amine), respectively. Comparative spectral analysis with the physical mixture (PTX and HPMC) showed shifts in peak positions, such as C=O stretching shifting from 1705.73 cm^{-1} to 1778.98 cm^{-1} and C-H stretching from 2949.59 cm^{-1} to 2877.27 cm^{-1} .

Despite these shifts, the prominent functional peaks of PTX and excipients remained identifiable, indicating no significant interaction between the drug and the excipients.

CONSTRUCTION OF CALIBRATION CURVE:

A standard stock solution of Pentoxifylline (1 mg/mL) was prepared by dissolving 100 mg in 100 mL of distilled water. A working standard solution (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was obtained by diluting 0.1 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with ethanol. For λ max determination, 1 mL of the working solution was diluted to 10 mL with distilled water (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and

scanned between 200-400 nm, identifying 275 nm as the maximum absorbance wavelength. A calibration curve was prepared by diluting the working solution to obtain concentrations of 0.1-0.5 µg/mL, measuring absorbance at 275 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The calibration curve showed a linear relationship, confirming Beer-Lambert's Law, and enabling the determination of unknown concentrations using the equation of the line. (20)

EVALUATION STUDIES:

pH:

The pH values of all four formulations were found to be relatively neutral, indicating that they fall within a range that is neither strongly acidic nor alkaline. Specifically, Formulations F1 and F2 displayed slightly lower pH levels, suggesting a mild acidity, while Formulations F3 and F4 exhibited slightly higher pH values, indicating a mild alkalinity. These slight variations in pH may have implications for the stability, effectiveness, or skin compatibility of the formulations, depending on their intended use. However, the overall neutral pH values suggest that these formulations are likely designed to be gentle and non-irritating for their intended application.

EVAPORATION TIME:

When comparing the evaporation times of all four formulations, it was observed that Formulation F2 demonstrated the shortest evaporation time, taking just 1 minute to fully evaporate. This suggests that F2 may have a higher volatility or a more efficient solvent system that allows for quicker evaporation. On the other hand, Formulations F3 and F4 exhibited longer evaporation times, indicating that these formulations might contain ingredients that slow down the evaporation process, such as more viscous solvents or higher amounts of water content. The difference in evaporation times could be significant depending on the intended use of the formulations. For instance, a shorter evaporation time could be advantageous for applications requiring fast-drying properties, while longer evaporation times may be beneficial for products that need to remain on the surface for a prolonged period, providing extended release or better coverage. (21)

THICKNESS:

All four formulations displayed uniform thickness, with each measuring at 0.1 mm, ensuring consistent film formation across the different products. This uniformity in thickness is crucial for ensuring that the formulations perform in a predictable and reliable manner when applied, providing an even coating on the intended surface or skin. A consistent 0.1 mm thickness helps to maintain the stability and integrity of the film, ensuring that it doesn't peel, crack, or unevenly distribute over time. Furthermore, such uniformity is important for achieving the desired functionality of the formulations, such as controlled release of active ingredients, consistent protection, or effective adhesion. Overall, the uniform film thickness enhances the overall quality and performance of the formulations, making them more effective for their intended applications.(22)

MOISTURE CONTENT:

All four formulations demonstrated low moisture content, ranging from 3% to 3.9%. This low moisture content is advantageous because it helps to inhibit the growth of microorganisms, such as bacteria, fungi, or mold, which typically thrive in higher moisture environments. By maintaining moisture levels within this range, the formulations are better preserved, reducing the risk of contamination and ensuring a longer shelf life. Moreover, the low moisture content contributes to the overall stability of the formulations, helping to preserve their integrity during storage by preventing degradation or changes in texture. This characteristic is especially important for ensuring that the products maintain their intended properties and effectiveness over time.

DRUG CONTENT PER SPRAY:

Formulation F2 exhibited the highest drug content per spray, with a concentration of 51.87 micrograms per milliliter, followed closely by F1, which contained 48.56 micrograms per milliliter. These results indicate efficient drug loading within the formulations, meaning that a substantial amount of the active ingredient is effectively incorporated into each spray. This high drug content per spray suggests that F2, in particular, has a more concentrated delivery of the active compound, potentially enhancing its

therapeutic efficacy per application. The slightly lower drug content in F1 still indicates a high level of drug incorporation, ensuring that both formulations are capable of delivering a sufficient dose for their intended use. Efficient drug loading is crucial in ensuring that the product performs optimally, providing the desired effects while potentially reducing the frequency of application or the amount of product required.

IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE:

Formulation F2 demonstrated the most favorable drug release profile, with an impressive 95.2% of the drug being released over a 300-minute period. This suggests that F2 is highly efficient in terms of controlled and sustained drug release. The gradual

and continuous release over this extended duration allows for a steady supply of the active ingredient, potentially improving therapeutic efficacy and maintaining consistent drug levels in the target area over time. Such a release pattern is particularly beneficial in applications where prolonged drug action is desired, such as in treatments requiring extended exposure or controlled dosing. The high percentage of drug release also indicates that the formulation is well-designed to optimize the bioavailability of the active compound, ensuring effective therapeutic outcomes. Overall, F2's favorable drug release profile makes it a promising formulation for applications that require sustained action or a long-lasting effect. (23).

RESULTS:

Figure 1: FT-IR spectra of Pentoxifylline drug

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of HPMC 100

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of Pentoxifylline with HPMC 100

S. NO	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance at 275nm
1.	0.1	0.021
2.	0.2	0.152
3.	0.3	0.276
4.	0.4	0.402
5.	0.5	0.530

Table 4: Absorbance and Concentration of Pentoxifylline

Figure 4: Calibration curve of Pentoxifylline

Table 5: Percentage% cumulative drug release

Time (mins)	% Cumulative Drug Release			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
30	21.4	22.1	15.4	17.6
60	40.4	42.5	18.3	20.3
90	49.5	50.7	22.7	24.4
120	75.8	77.4	35.2	37.6
180	80.3	81.3	47.7	52.8
240	85.5	87.2	62.8	72.8
300	93.6	95.2	74.2	78.6

Figure 5: IN-vitro drug release of Pentoxifylline**DISCUSSION:**

The study successfully developed and evaluated four film-forming spray formulations (F1–F4) containing PTX for topical application, focusing on their physicochemical properties, drug content, and release profile. All formulations exhibited a skin-compatible pH range of 4.7–5.75, aligning with the natural pH of human skin, which is crucial for minimizing irritation and ensuring compatibility. The moderate viscosity (212–219 cP) facilitated ease of application, allowing for uniform distribution and adherence to the skin surface without excessive thickness or resistance to spreading. Additionally, the formulations had low moisture content (3.02%–3.95%), effectively preventing microbial growth and enhancing storage stability.

A uniform film thickness of 0.1 mm was achieved across all formulations, ensuring consistent coverage, protection, and controlled drug release. Evaporation time varied among the formulations, with F2

exhibiting the shortest evaporation time of just 1 minute, indicating a faster drying and film-forming capability. In contrast, F3 and F4 had longer evaporation times, potentially prolonging the retention of the formulation on the skin surface.

Drug content analysis revealed that F2 had the highest drug concentration per spray (51.87 µg/mL), followed closely by F1 (48.56 µg/mL), demonstrating efficient drug loading. The drug release study indicated that F2 exhibited the most favorable sustained release profile, with 95.2% of the drug being released over 300 minutes. This prolonged drug permeation suggests an extended duration of therapeutic action, ensuring sustained bioavailability and effectiveness in wound healing or other topical applications.

The findings indicate that the formulated film-forming sprays successfully incorporated Pentoxifylline, achieving favorable physicochemical properties, efficient drug loading, and sustained drug release. Among the four formulations, F2 emerged as

the most promising, demonstrating enhanced bioavailability, reduced systemic side effects, and improved therapeutic efficacy. Its rapid drying, high drug content, and sustained release profile make it particularly suitable for topical applications, including wound healing. This novel approach provides a convenient, effective, and patient-friendly method for localized Pentoxifylline delivery, potentially improving treatment outcomes and patient compliance.

SUMMARY:

The study evaluated four film-forming spray formulations (F1–F4) containing Pentoxifylline (PTX) for topical use. All formulations had skin-compatible pH, moderate viscosity, low moisture content, and uniform film thickness. F2 dried the quickest (1 minute), had the highest drug content (51.87 µg/mL), and showed the best sustained release (95.2% over 300 minutes). F2 emerged as the most promising formulation, offering enhanced bioavailability, reduced side effects, and improved efficacy for wound healing, providing an effective, patient-friendly method for localized PTX delivery.

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